

Effect of Cuff Fabric Material on Oscillometric Blood Pressure Measurements; A Dynamic Numerical Study

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Abstract— This study investigates the effect of cuff material elasticity on oscillometric blood pressure (BP) measurement. Increased stiffness of the cuff fabric (154 to 300 MPa) decreases the wavelength of buckling pattern leading to more localised and sharper buckling behaviour. The cuff pressure could be different than applied pressure on arm and is dependent upon the material of cuff. The change in buckling pattern causes non-uniform pressure transmission affecting the arterial deformation and oscillations pattern that in turn compromises the accuracy of BP measurement.

Clinical Relevance— Variations in cuff fabric could incur variations in oscillometric BP measurements. Cuffs made of different fabrics are not replaceable and signify need for standardization of cuff design and material.

I. INTRODUCTION

Oscillometric blood pressure (BP) measurements use a pressurized cuff wrapped around arm that captures artery's deformations against cuff pressure as pressure oscillations. Change in the pattern of oscillations against cuff pressure is exploited to estimate BP non-invasively. The estimation varies depending on biomechanical factors as reported in literature [1, 2] through simulated oscillometric waveforms. These studies on simulated oscillometric waveforms assume uniform pressure without taking cuff buckling into account. Pressure registered as cuff pressure is different than pressure exerted on the arm's surface and ultimately artery, due to buckling of cuff's inner layer, resulting in varied pattern of oscillations. This study employs an upper arm model [1] with a cuff wrapped around and simulates oscillometric waveforms to investigate the effect of the elastic modulus of the cuff on oscillometric BP measurement.

II. METHOD

A human upper arm and cuff were modelled in ABAQUS® 2024, upper arm geometry was accessed from Ref. [1], to simulate oscillometric waveforms. Hyper-elastic material properties of the brachial artery were taken from Ref. [3]. The applied arterial pressure was 110/70 mmHg and cuff was inflated above systole (150 mmHg) and linearly deflated below diastole at a rate of 5 mmHg/s with total maneuver of 40 seconds. The arterial lumen area changes were tracked for the deflation cycle, and an oscillometric waveform was generated.

III. RESULTS

Pressure applied on arm's surface is non-uniform with cuff on, uniform pressure assumed to simulate oscillometric waveforms is unrealistic and leads to shift in maximum amplitude of oscillometric envelopes as shown in Fig. 1(f)

that potentially results in an overestimation of mean arterial pressure. This non-uniformity of pressure is due to cuff buckling that generates localised pressure variations in the soft tissue, Fig. 1(b), (d). Further, the buckling pattern varies as the cuff properties change from $E = 300$ MPa [Fig. 1(b)] to $E = 154$ MPa [Fig. 1(d)]. Pressure transmission changes with a change in buckling wave for different cuff materials, this results in varied oscillation patterns and affects BP estimations.

Figure 1 Cuff buckling effect on oscillometric BP measurements, (a) cuff buckling and (b) pressure distribution in tissue for cuff fabric $E= 300$ MPa; (c) cuff buckling and (d) pressure distribution in tissue for cuff fabric $E= 154$ MPa; (e) artery oscillations (area changes) and (f) shift in envelope of area changes with and without cuff.

IV. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Earlier studies assumed uniform cuff pressure [1], while buckling of cuff results in varied pressure patterns. When cuff material changes the buckling wave around tissue also changes resulting in varied pressure transmission to the brachial artery. Artery deformations are affected by the crest or trough of the buckling wave being right above the tissue where the artery is embedded, as pressure accumulates near the buckled part. Therefore, effect on artery deformations results in varied patterns of oscillations. The study concludes that cuffs of different fabrics are not replaceable, only standard cuffs on a device must be used.

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